

Vital Pulp Therapy: An Overview and Current Trends

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Abstract

Vital pulp therapy (VPT) is a dental procedure aimed at preserving the health and vitality of the dental pulp. This treatment is primarily employed in cases of pulpal exposure resulting from carious lesions, trauma, or dental procedures. The main objective of VPT is to maintain the pulp's vitality, promote healing, and prevent the progression of pulpitis, which can lead to the need for more invasive treatments like root canal therapy. VPT techniques typically involve the removal of the affected tissue, followed by the application of biocompatible materials to protect the pulp and encourage its healing. Recent advances in vital pulp therapy reflect a shift towards more biologically-based and patient-centered approaches. The integration of innovative materials, regenerative techniques, and advanced technologies has significantly improved the outcomes of VPT. As research continues to evolve, the future of vital pulp therapy holds great promise for enhancing dental care and preserving the vitality of the dental pulp in affected teeth.

Introduction

Vital pulp therapy (VPT) is a dental procedure aimed at preserving the health and vitality of the dental pulp. The dental pulp is a soft tissue located within the centre of a tooth. This treatment is primarily employed in cases of pulpal exposure resulting from carious lesions, trauma, or dental procedures. The main objective of VPT is to maintain the pulp's vitality, promote healing, and prevent the progression of pulpitis, which can lead to the need for more invasive treatments like root canal therapy.

The dental pulp plays a crucial role in the overall health of a tooth by providing its sensory innervation and nourishment. When the pulpal tissue becomes compromised, prompt intervention is essential to avoid irreversible damage. VPT techniques typically involve the removal of the affected tissue, followed by the application of biocompatible materials to protect the pulp and encourage its healing.¹

Objectives of Vital Pulp Therapy

- 1. Preserve Vitality:** The primary goal is to keep the pulpal tissue alive and functional, allowing for continued tooth development and health of the pulp tissue.
- 2. Promote Healing:** VPT aims to facilitate the natural healing processes of the pulp tissue and support the regeneration of dentin.
- 3. Prevent Infection:** By sealing the pulp and eliminating sources of infection, VPT reduces the risk of further complications.¹

Indications for Vital Pulp Therapy

VPT is indicated in various clinical scenarios, including:

- **Pulp Exposure:** Caused by deep carious lesions or trauma.
- **Reversible Pulpitis:** When the pulp is inflamed but still viable.
- **Young Permanent Teeth:** Especially in cases where root development is incomplete.²

The growing understanding of dental pulp biology and the regenerative potential of pulp tissues has led to innovative approaches that extend beyond the traditional

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methods. Today, VPT not only focuses on protecting the pulp but also emphasizes the regeneration of the pulp-dentin complex. This shift in perspective is particularly relevant for young patients with developing teeth, where preserving the pulp vitality is crucial for proper root development.³

Recent Advancements in Vital Pulp Therapy

Bioactive Materials: The development of new bioactive materials, such as calcium silicate cements, has improved the outcomes of VPT. These materials promote pulp healing, support mineralization, and enhance the sealing ability of the treatment.¹

Some commonly used bioactive materials are

Mineral Trioxide Aggregate (MTA)

- **Composition:** MTA is composed of tricalcium silicate, dicalcium silicate, calcium sulfate, and bismuth oxide.
- **Advantages:** MTA is known for its excellent sealing properties, biocompatibility, and ability to promote hard tissue formation. It encourages the formation of a dentin bridge, providing a protective barrier for the pulp.
- **Applications:** MTA is widely used for pulp capping and as a retrograde filling material in endodontics.¹³

Calcium Silicate Cements

- **Examples:** Biodentine and EndoSequence Root Repair Material.
- **Advantages:** These materials exhibit good mechanical properties, biocompatibility, and the ability to stimulate mineralization. They are designed to facilitate dentin regeneration and support pulp healing.
- **Applications:** Calcium silicate cements are used in direct and indirect pulp capping procedures.¹³

Glass Ionomer Cements (GICs)

- **Composition:** GIC is composed of fluoro-aluminosilicate glass powder and polyacrylic acid liquid.
- **Advantages:** GICs provide good adhesion to dentin, release fluoride, and exhibit bioactivity that can enhance the remineralization of the surrounding dentin.

- **Applications:** They are often used in non-vital pulp therapy and as liners and bases in restorative procedures.⁴

Hydroxyapatite-Based Materials

- **Properties:** Hydroxyapatite is a naturally occurring mineral form of calcium apatite that mimics the mineral content of bone and teeth.
- **Advantages:** These materials support mineralization and can integrate with existing dental tissues, promoting pulp healing and repair.
- **Applications:** Used in regenerative procedures and as components of bioactive pulp capping materials.⁵
- **Chitosan and Other Natural Polymers**
- **Properties:** Chitosan is a natural biopolymer derived from chitin, known for its biocompatibility and biodegradability.
- **Advantages:** It promotes cell adhesion, proliferation, differentiation and supports tissue regeneration.
- **Applications:** Chitosan-based scaffolds are being researched for their potential in pulp tissue engineering.⁵
- **Bioactive Glass**
- **Properties:** Bioactive glass can bond to hard tissues and release ions that promote healing.
- **Advantages:** It stimulates mineralization and can enhance the biological response of dental tissues.
- **Applications:** Bioactive glass materials are used in regenerative endodontics and for pulp capping.¹³

Strategies for Regenerative Endodontics

- Stem Cell Research:** Advances in regenerative medicine have highlighted the role of dental pulp stem cells (DPSCs) in promoting tissue regeneration. Studies are being conducted to utilize these stem cells in combination with scaffolds to facilitate pulp repair and regeneration.^{5,6}

Gronthos et al. first isolated DPSCs from adult human dental pulp. In *in vivo* studies, it has been seen that DPSCs produces dental pulp-like tissue surrounded by odontoblast-like cells and a dentin-like structure. DPSCs are clonogenically efficient, capable of multi-lineage differentiation, and capable of self-renewal. Comparably, when human exfoliated deciduous teeth (SHEDs) were originally identified, Miura et al. revealed that the SHEDs' stem cells were extremely proliferative and could differentiate into a variety of cell types, such as odontoblasts, adipocytes, and neural cells. The phenotypic profile of MSCs is shared by SHED and DPSCs, and they both express several common MSC markers, including CD44, CD73, CD90, and CD166.^{7,9,10}

- Scaffold Technologies:** Innovative scaffold designs,

including 3D-printed and natural polymer scaffolds, provide a supportive environment for cell growth and differentiation, enhancing the regenerative potential of VPT.⁸

Natural Polymer Scaffolds

Collagen

- **Properties:** Collagen is a natural protein that constitutes a significant part of the extracellular matrix (ECM) in dental tissues. It provides excellent biocompatibility and supports cell adhesion.
- **Applications:** Collagen scaffolds can enhance cell growth and differentiation, making them suitable for pulp regeneration.⁵

Chitosan

- **Properties:** Derived from chitin, chitosan is biodegradable and exhibits antibacterial properties. It is biocompatible and supports cell adhesion.
- **Applications:** Chitosan scaffolds can be used in conjunction with growth factors to promote pulp healing and regeneration.⁸

Alginate

- **Properties:** Alginate is a natural polysaccharide that forms hydrogels, providing a moist environment that is conducive to cell proliferation.
- **Applications:** Alginate scaffolds can be used for cell encapsulation and release, making them suitable for delivering stem cells and growth factors.⁵

Synthetic Polymer Scaffolds

● Polylactic Acid (PLA) and Polylactic-co-glycolic Acid (PLGA)

- **Properties:** These biodegradable polymers are commonly used in tissue engineering due to their tunable mechanical properties and degradation rates.
- **Applications:** PLA and PLGA scaffolds can be designed with controlled porosity to enhance cell infiltration and growth.¹²

● Polycaprolactone (PCL)

- **Properties:** PCL is a biodegradable polymer with excellent mechanical properties and slow degradation rates.
- **Applications:** PCL scaffolds can provide long-term support for pulp regeneration, allowing for gradual integration with surrounding tissues.¹²

● Ceramic Scaffolds

● Hydroxyapatite (HA)

- **Properties:** HA is a bioceramic that closely resembles the mineral component of bone and teeth. It promotes mineralization and osteoconduction.
- **Applications:** HA scaffolds can support dental pulp regeneration by providing a conducive environment for mineralized tissue formation.¹²

● Bioactive Glass

- **Properties:** Bioactive glass can bond to hard tissues and release ions that promote healing and regeneration.
- **Applications:** These scaffolds are effective in facilitating the repair of dental tissues and stimulating biological responses.¹³

3D-Printed Scaffolds

- **Customized Designs:** Advances in 3D printing technology allow for the creation of scaffolds tailored to specific

clinical needs, including size, shape, and porosity.

- **Applications:** 3D-printed scaffolds can be designed to replicate the natural architecture of pulp tissue, enhancing the potential for successful regeneration.¹²

Incorporation of Stem Cells and Growth Factors

The effectiveness of scaffolds in VPT can be enhanced by incorporating dental pulp stem cells (DPSCs) or other mesenchymal stem cells, along with growth factors such as:

- **Transforming Growth Factor-beta (TGF-β):** Promotes cell differentiation and tissue repair.
- **Vascular Endothelial Growth Factor (VEGF):** Stimulates angiogenesis, which is essential for supplying nutrients to regenerating tissue.

The use of growth factors and signaling molecules, such as TGF-β and VEGF, in VPT protocols is being explored to stimulate healing and promote angiogenesis in the pulp tissue.¹⁰

Key Growth Factors Used in Vital Pulp Therapy

1. Transforming Growth Factor-beta (TGF-β)

- **Function:** TGF-β is involved in the regulation of cell growth, differentiation, and extracellular matrix production. It is essential for the healing process and plays a significant role in tissue regeneration.

● Role in VPT:

- Stimulates the proliferation of dental pulp stem cells (DPSCs).
- Promotes the differentiation of odontoblast-like cells, which are crucial for dentin formation.
- Enhances the synthesis of extracellular matrix components, supporting the structural integrity of regenerated tissue.²

2. Vascular Endothelial Growth Factor (VEGF)

- **Function:** VEGF is a key regulator of angiogenesis, the process of new blood vessel formation. It also promotes endothelial cell proliferation and migration.

● Role in VPT:

- Stimulates angiogenesis in the pulp tissue, ensuring an adequate blood supply for healing.
- Supports the survival and function of DPSCs by providing necessary nutrients and oxygen.
- Enhances the overall regenerative potential of the pulp-dentin complex.⁵

3. Bone Morphogenetic Proteins (BMPs)

- **Function:** BMPs are a group of growth factors that induce the formation of bone and cartilage. They play a crucial role in regulating cellular processes in various tissues, including dental pulp.

● Role in VPT

- Promote osteogenic differentiation of mesenchymal stem cells, which can contribute to the formation of new dentin.
- Enhance the reparative processes within the dental pulp.
- Specifically, BMP-2 and BMP-7 have been investigated for their potential in stimulating pulp regeneration.⁹

4. Fibroblast Growth Factor (FGF)

- **Function:** FGFs are a family of growth factors involved in cell proliferation, differentiation, and angiogenesis.

- **Role in VPT:**
 - Promote the proliferation and differentiation of pulp cells.
 - Enhance angiogenesis and the formation of a vascular network within the pulp.
 - Support the overall healing process by improving tissue response to injury.¹⁰

5. Platelet-Derived Growth Factor (PDGF)

- **Function:** PDGF plays a crucial role in cell growth and proliferation, particularly in mesenchymal and endothelial cells.
- **Role in VPT:**
 - Stimulates the migration and proliferation of DPSCs and other progenitor cells.
 - Enhances tissue repair processes by promoting angiogenesis and extracellular matrix synthesis.
 - Involved in the regulation of inflammation during the healing response.⁹

6. Insulin-like Growth Factor (IGF)

- **Function:** IGF is involved in cell growth, differentiation, and survival. It mediates many of the growth-promoting effects of insulin and growth hormone.
- **Role in VPT:**
 - Supports the proliferation and survival of pulp cells.
 - Enhances collagen synthesis and extracellular matrix production, critical for tissue regeneration.
 - Plays a role in modulating the inflammatory response in the pulp tissue.⁵

Delivery Methods for Growth Factors

The effectiveness of growth factors in vital pulp therapy depends on their delivery method and formulation. Several strategies have been developed, including:

1. **Direct Application:** Growth factors can be applied directly to the pulp tissue during the procedure, either as standalone agents or incorporated into bioactive materials.
 2. **Hydrogels:** Biocompatible hydrogels can be used to encapsulate growth factors, allowing for controlled release and sustained delivery over time.
 3. **Scaffold Integration:** Combining growth factors with scaffolds (natural or synthetic) can enhance the regenerative environment, facilitating the migration and differentiation of stem cells.
 4. **Platelet-Rich Plasma (PRP):** PRP is a concentrate of platelets derived from a patient's blood, rich in growth factors such as PDGF, VEGF, and TGF- β . PRP can be used to enhance the healing process in VPT.¹¹
- C. **Laser Therapy:** The application of laser technology in VPT offers potential benefits in terms of pulp disinfection, reduction of inflammation, and promotion of healing.

Lasers work by emitting concentrated light energy that can be absorbed by specific tissues, leading to photothermal or photochemical effects. In the context of VPT, lasers can:

Disinfection: Lasers can effectively reduce bacterial load in the pulp chamber and root canal system, minimizing the risk of infection.

Ablation: Lasers can precisely remove infected or

damaged tissue without significant damage to surrounding healthy tissue.

Healing: Certain laser wavelengths can promote cellular activity and enhance the healing process in the pulp and surrounding tissues.¹⁴

Types of Lasers Used in Vital Pulp Therapy

1. Diode Lasers

- **Wavelength:** Typically between 800 to 980 nm.
- **Advantages:** Diode lasers are portable, easy to use, and versatile. They can effectively disinfect pulp tissue and promote hemostasis.
- **Applications:** Commonly used for soft tissue procedures, tissue ablation, and disinfection during VPT.

2. Erbium Lasers (Er:YAG/Er, Cr:YSGG)

- **Wavelength:** Er lasers emit light at 2940 nm, while Er,Cr lasers operate at 2780 nm.
- **Advantages:** These lasers have a high affinity for water, making them effective for cutting and ablation of soft and hard tissues with minimal thermal damage.
- **Applications:** Used for precise removal of carious dentin, disinfection of the pulp chamber, and preparation of the canal space.

3. CO₂ Lasers

- **Wavelength:** Emits light at 10,600 nm.
- **Advantages:** CO₂ lasers are highly effective for soft tissue procedures due to their high water absorption, leading to efficient tissue vaporization.
- **Applications:** Primarily used for soft tissue surgeries and periodontal procedures but can also be utilized in VPT for pulpal disinfection and hemostasis.

4. Nd:YAG

- **Wavelength:** Emits light at 1064 nm.
- **Advantages:** Nd lasers penetrate hard tissues and can be used for both soft and hard tissue applications.
- **Applications:** Useful in disinfection of root canals and promoting pulp healing due to their ability to stimulate tissue regeneration.¹⁴

Applications of Lasers in Vital Pulp Therapy

1. Pulp Disinfection:

- Lasers can significantly reduce bacterial counts in the pulp chamber and root canal, leading to a cleaner environment for subsequent procedures. The high-energy light destroys bacteria without causing damage to healthy tissue.

2. Tissue Ablation:

- Lasers can precisely remove necrotic or infected tissue from the pulp chamber and canals. This precision minimizes trauma to surrounding healthy tissues, making the procedure less invasive.

3. Hemostasis:

- Lasers can effectively control bleeding during procedures by coagulating blood vessels. This property is particularly useful when dealing with inflamed or damaged tissues.

4. Promotion of Healing:

- Certain wavelengths of lasers can stimulate cellular activity and promote tissue regeneration. This is particularly beneficial in cases where pulp vitality needs

to be preserved.

- **5. Reduction of Post-Operative Pain and Inflammation:**
- The use of lasers has been associated with reduced pain and swelling post-treatment, contributing to improved patient comfort.

Advantages of Lasers in Vital Pulp Therapy

- **Precision:** Lasers allow for precise targeting of tissues, minimizing damage to surrounding healthy structures.
- **Minimized Trauma:** The minimally invasive nature of laser treatments can result in less postoperative discomfort and quicker recovery times.
- **Reduced Infection Risk:** The antimicrobial properties of lasers help to lower the risk of postoperative infections.
- **Enhanced Treatment Outcomes:** Improved disinfection and the ability to promote healing contribute to better overall treatment success rates.¹⁴

Limitations and Considerations

- **Cost:** Laser systems can be expensive, and the initial investment may not be feasible for all dental practices.
- **Training:** Dentists must receive proper training to use lasers effectively and safely. Understanding the appropriate settings for different procedures is crucial.
- **Treatment Depth:** The penetration depth of laser energy can vary based on the type of laser and tissue, so careful consideration of laser selection and application technique is essential.¹⁴

D. Personalized Approaches

- Emerging concepts in personalized medicine have begun to influence VPT. Tailoring treatment approaches based on individual patient factors, such as age, tooth maturity, and the extent of pulp damage, can lead to improved outcomes.
- a. **Genetic and Molecular Considerations**
 - Research is exploring the genetic and molecular profiles of patients to predict responses to VPT and tailor treatments accordingly.
- b. **Biomarkers** Identifying biomarkers that indicate the state of the pulp and its regenerative potential can inform treatment decisions and enhance the success of VPT.⁴

Conclusion

Recent advances in vital pulp therapy reflect a shift towards more biologically-based and patient-centered approaches. The integration of innovative materials, regenerative techniques, and advanced technologies has significantly improved the outcomes of VPT. As research continues to evolve, the future of vital pulp therapy holds great promise for

enhancing dental care and preserving the vitality of the dental pulp in affected teeth. These advancements not only improve clinical success rates but also contribute to better patient comfort and overall treatment experiences.⁷

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